

A REVIEW ON POLYHERBAL FACE PACK

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the Review preparation and evaluation of a polyherbal face pack using natural ingredients such as Multani Mitti, Turmeric, Aloe Vera, Sandalwood, Neem Powder, Orange Peel Powder, Nutmeg, Rose Petals, Honey, Almond, Tulasi, and Green Tea Powder. Facial skin is continuously exposed to environmental pollutants, dust, microorganisms, and harmful ultraviolet radiation, which may lead to acne, pigmentation, premature aging, and other skin disorders. Herbal face packs have gained significant importance due to their safety, effectiveness, and minimal side effects when compared to synthetic cosmetic products. The selected herbal ingredients possess various beneficial properties based on literature antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, moisturizing, cleansing, and skin-nourishing activities. Further investigation have to be studied.

KEYWORDS: Herbal facepacks, moisturizing, antimicrobial, Antioxidant, skin nourishing.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are defined as the source which are sprinkled applied or poured on the skin to improve the beautiness color & attractiveness to our skin when applied in small quantities Herbal face packs are cost effective and have no side effects to get fair skin naturally present review article deals with the preparation and evaluation of herbal face pack for radiant skin

based herbal ingredients like Rose petals, Honey, Tulasi, Neem, Almond, Multani Matti, turmeric, Aloe vera, sandalwood, orange peel, green tea powder. Various skin types require various kinds of herbal face packs. Homemade natural face packs and masks make way for smooth, healthy skin.

HERBAL INGREDIENTS USED IN FACE PACK

MATERIALS

Collection of Materials: The various herbal sources of Materials were collected from the medicinal garden, local super market & surroundings of Dhanvanthari institute of pharmaceutical sciences, sujathanagar, Kothagudem.

S.no	Name of the Compound	scientific name	Pictures	Genus	uses
01	Multani Matti	Fullers earth		Solum fullonum	Skin care, hair care, dandruff, itchiness.
02	Turmeric	Curcuma longa		Curcuma longa	Anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, cancer treatment, inhibit cancer cell growth, inducing apoptosis.
03	Aloe vera	Aloe		Aloe	Skin care, wound healing, Digestive health, oral health, anti-inflammatory, hair care, anti-microbial and cosmetics.
04	Sandal wood	Santalum album		Santalum	Anti-microbial, anti-septic, sleep-aid, anti-septic and anti-inflammatory

					properties.
05	Orange peel	Citrus Sinesis		Citrus	Stress relief, skin care, anti-microbial and anti-fungal.
06	Neem powder	Azadirachta indica		Azadirachta indica	Insecticide, replicant, dental care, anti-viral, reduces plaque.
07	Nutmeg Myristicafragrams	Myristicafragrams		Myristicafragrams	Relieves indigestion, nausea, ese tooth acne pain, reduces anxiety and stress.
08	Rose petal powder	Rosa		Rosa	Smoothness, menstrual cramps, promotes skin health, improves mood.
09	Honey	Apis		Apis	Anti-microbial, wound healing, anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory, cough.
10	Tulasi	Ocimum tenuiflorum		ocimum	Treating Anemia, anti acne, anti Anxiety, immunity booster, cough reliever, Digestive aid

11	Almond	Prunus dulcis		Prunus	Treating Anemia, Anxiety and skin condition.
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01. MULTANI MATTI (CALCIUM BENTONITE)

Scientific name: *Fuller's earth*

Order: Lamiales

Genus: - *solum fullonum*

Family: - Lamiaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Silica (SiO₂): 50-70%, Alumina (AL₂O₃): 10-20%, Iron oxide (FE₂O₃)²-5%, Calcium oxide (CaO): 2-5%, Magnesium oxide(MgO): 1-3%, Potassium Oxide (K₂O): 1-2%, Sodium Oxide(Na₂O): 1-2%, Water(H₂O): 5-10%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Hydrate Aluminium Silicate: The main component of Multani Matti, which gives it its absorbant properties.

Calcium Bentonite: A component of multanimatti, which is similar to bentonite clay.

Kaolinite: A type of clay mineral that is known for its soothing and calming properties.

Therapeutic uses

SKIN CARE: Multani Matti is used to treat various skin conditions, such as acne, pimples, and blackheads.

HAIR CARE: Multani Matti is used to treat dandruff, itchiness, and other scalp problems.

DETOXIFICATION: Multani Matti is used to detoxify the body by absorbing toxins, heavy metals, and other impurities from the skin and scalp.

02. TURMERIC (CARCUMA LONGA)

Scientific name: *Curcuma longa*

Order: - Zingiberales

Genus: -Curcuma

Family: -Zingiberaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENT

Curcuminoids: 2-5%, volatile oil: 5-10%, Polysaccharides: 10-20%, Minerals: 5-10%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Curcumin: The main active ingredient in turmeric which can make up to 5% of spice.

Demethoxycurcumin: The curcuminoid with potent anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant properties.

Volatile oils: The aroma of turmeric comes from alpha and beta turmerones and aromatic turmerones.

Therapeutic uses

ANTI-INFLAMMATORY: Turmeric contains curcumin, which has potent anti-inflammatory properties, reducing inflammation and alleviating symptoms of condition like arthritis.

ANTI OXIDANT: Turmeric curcumin as antioxidant properties, protecting against oxidative stress.

CANCER PREVENTION: Turmeric curcumin has been inhibiting cancer cell growth and inducing apoptosis.

03. ALOE VERA [ALOE BARBENDIS]

Scientific name: *Aloe*

Order: -Asparaguses

Genus: - Aloe

Family: - Liliacee.

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Polysaccharides: 10-20%, Glyco proteins: 5-10%, Anthra quinones: 2-5%, Vitamins and minerals: 1-5%, Fatty acids: 1-5%.

Active constituents

Aloin: An anthra quinone with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant ad anti-microbial properties.

Aloe-emodin: An anthraquinone with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant ad anti-microbial properties.

Lectins: Glyco-proteins with anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties.

Therapeutic uses

SKIN CARE: - Aloe vera is used to treat various skin conditions, such as burns, wounds, eczema and acne

COSMETIC USES: - Aloe vera is used in various cosmetic products, such as lotions, shampoos, and conditions.

ORAL HEALTH: - Aloe vera has been shown to reduce plaques, prevent tooth decay and soothe mouth ulcer.

04. SANDAL WOOD(SANTALUM ALBA)

Scientific name: *Santalum album*

Order: Santalales

Genus: Santalum

Family: Santalaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Sesquiterpenes: 70-80%, Mono terpenes: 10-20%, Phenolic components: 5-10%, Aldehydes: 2-5%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Santalol: A sesquiterpene with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Berganotol: A sesquiterpene with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant properties

Therapeutic uses

ANTI-MICROBIAL: Sandalwood oil has anti-microbial properties, which help prevents the growth of micro-organisms, reducing the risk infection.

ANTISEPTIC: Sandalwood oil has antiseptic and anti-inflammatory properties, making it effective in treating skin condition.

SLEEP AID: It is helping to improve sleep quality.

05. ORANGE PEEL

Scientific Name: *Citrus Aurantium dulcis*

Order: Sapindales

Genus: Citrus

Family: Rutaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Essential oils: 2-5%, Flavonoids: 1-3%, Limonoids: 1-2%, Carotenoids: 0.5 – 1.5%, Pectin: 10-20%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Hesperidin: A flavonoid with anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, cardiovascular / protective properties.

Limonin: A limonoid with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Limonene: A monoterpene with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Therapeutic uses

STRESS RELIEF: Orange peel has a calming effect on the mind and body, reducing stress and anxiety level.

SKIN CARE: Orange peel is used in skin care products due to its antiseptics and anti-fungal properties.

ANTI MICROBIAL: Orange peel has antimicrobial properties, which help to prevent the growth of macro-organisms, reducing risk of infections.

06. NEEM POWDER

Scientific Name: *Azadirachta indica*

Order: - Sapindales

Genus: - Azadirachta

Family: - Meliaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Triterpenoids: 10-20%, Flavonoids: 5-10%, phenolic acid: 2-5%, Essential oils: 1-3%, Saponins: 1-2%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Azadirachtin: The most abundant active constituent in neem leaves.

Nimbin: A tetranortriterpenoid found in the bark of the neem plant.

Beta-Sitosterol: The polyphenolic flavonoid found in neem leaves. It has anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties.

Therapeutic uses

INSECTICIDE AND REPELLENT: Neem powder is used as a natural insecticide and repellent, effective against mosquitoes and pests.

DENTAL CARE: Neem powder is used in dental care products to reduce plaque, prevent tooth-decay and soothe mouth ulcers.

ANTI VIRAL: It is effective against various virus.

07. NUTMEG

Scientific name: *Myristica fragrans* houtt.

Order: - Magnoliales

Species: - *Myristica fragrans*

Family: - Myristicaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Essential oils: 10-15%, Phenolic compounds: 2-5% Alkaloids:2-5%, Fatty acids:30-40%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Myristicin: an essential oil with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, psycho active properties.

Elemicin: An essential oil with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Myristic acid: A fatty acid with anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant properties.

Therapeutic uses

RELIEVES INDIGESTION AND NAUSEA: *Myristica fragrans* oil has natural anti-inflammatory properties that may help alleviate digestive issues.

EASE TOOTH ACNE PAIN: *Myristica fragrans* oil has been used as a natural remedy for tooth acne pain due to its analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties.

REDUCES ANXIETY AND STRESS: The aroma of *Myristica* fragrance oil may have a calming effect on the mind and body, reducing anxiety and stress.

08. ROSE PETALS POWDER

Scientific name: *Rosa*

Order: - Rosales

Genus: -*Rosa*

Family: - Rosaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Essential oils: 1-3%, Flavanoids:5-10%, Phenolic acids:2-5%, Vitamins and minerals:1-5%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Geraniol: An essential oil with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Linalool: An essential oil with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and sedative properties.

Gallic acid: A phenolic acid with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial properties.

Therapeutic uses

SOOTHENS MENSTRUAL CRAMPS: The powder may help ease menstrual cramps, bloating and other symptoms associated with PMS due to its anti-spasmodic and anti-inflammatory properties.

PROMOTES SKIN HEALTH: Rose petals powder may help to reduce inflammation, improve skin texture, and promote wound healing due to its anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.

IMPROVES MOOD: The powder may help alleviate symptoms of depression, improve mood, and promote relaxation due to its anti-depressant and anxiolytic properties.

09. HONEY

Scientific name: - *Apis Mellifera Linnaeus*

Order: - Hymenoptera

Genus: - *Apis*

Family: - Apidae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Carbohydrates:70-80%, Water: 14-20%, Proteins: 0.5-1.5%, Minerals: 0.5-1.5%, Vitamins: 0.1-0.5%, Aromatic compounds: 0.1-0.5%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Flavonoids: A class of compounds with anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial properties.

Hydrogen peroxide: A natural anti-septic with anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties.

Bee defensin-1: A peptide with anti-microbial properties.

Therapeutic uses

Wound healing: Honey anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties can help promote wound healing and tissue repair.

Skin and hair care: Honeys moisturising and anti-bacterial properties make it a popular ingredient in skin care and hair care products.

Anti-microbial: Honeys acidity and hydrogen peroxide contain make it effective agent a range micro-organism, including bacteria, virus and fungi.

Allergy relief: Some studies suggest that consuming small amount of locally produced honey can help desensitize individual and local allergies

10. ALMOND

Scientific name: *Prunus dulcis*

Order: - Rosales

Genus: - Prunus

Family: - Rosaceae

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Lipids: 50-60%, Proteins:20-25%, Carbohydrates: 15-20%, Minerals: 5-10%, Vitamins: 1-5%.

ACTIVE CONSTITUENTS

Vitamin E: A fat-soluble vitamin with anti-oxidant properties.

Mono unsaturated fatty acids: A type of fatty acid with anti-inflammatory and cardiovascular protective properties.

Magnesium: A mineral with anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and cardiovascular protective properties.

Therapeutic uses

Cardio vascular health: Almonds are rich in mono-unsaturated fats, vitamin E and magnesium, which can help lower cholesterol level and reduce the risk of heart diseases.

Skin and hair care: Almond oil, extracted from almonds, is rich in vitamin A, B and E and can help, moisturize and nourish the skin and hair.

Immune system supportive: Almond contains Vitamin E which can help support immune function and reduce the risk of illness like common cold.

Weight management: Almonds are low in carbohydrates and high in healthy fats and protein, making them a nutrition's, snacks for those trying to manage their weight.

11: OCIMUM

Scientific name: Ocimum Sanctum

Species: Ocimum Tenuiflorum

Genus: Ocimum

Order: Limiales

Family: Lamiaceae

Therapeutic uses

Hair conditioner

Hair cleanser

Anti ageing,

Anti-Acne

Cathartic

CONCLUSION

In the present scenario, people need cure for certain skin problems without side effects. Herbal ingredients opened the way to formulate cosmetics without any side effects. Herbal face packs are considered as sustaining and protective way to advance the appearance of skin. Thus, in the present work, it is very good attempt to formulate the herbal face pack containing naturally available ingredients like Hibiscus, orange peel, Neem, Multanimitti, Sandle wood and Amla are safe further investigation have to be done.

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